
ON THE SOLVABILITY OF THE XOR PROBLEM BY SPIKING NEURAL NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

The linearly inseparable XOR problem and the related problem of representing binary logical gates is revisited from the point of view of temporal encoding and its solvability by spiking neural networks with minimal configurations of leaky integrate-and-fire (LIF) neurons. We use this problem as an example to study the effect of different hyper parameters such as information encoding, the number of hidden units in a fully connected reservoir, the choice of the leaky parameter and the reset mechanism in terms of reset-to-zero and reset-by-subtraction based on different refractory times. The distributions of the weight matrices give insight into the difficulty, respectively the probability, to find a solution. This leads to the observation that zero refractory time together with graded spikes and an adapted reset mechanism, reset-to-mod, makes it possible to realize sparse solutions of a minimal configuration with only two neurons in the hidden layer to resolve all binary logic gate constellations with XOR as a special case.

Keywords Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) · Leaky Integrate-and-Fire · Temporal Encoding · Reservoir Computing

1 Introduction

We consider the set $S = \{(0, 0), (0, 1), (1, 0), (1, 1)\}$ and all its binary partitions $P = [A, B]$, where $P = A \cup B$, $A \cap B = \emptyset$. XOR represents the special partition $P_{\text{XOR}} := [\{(0, 0), (1, 1)\}, \{(0, 1), (1, 0)\}]$. Solving the XOR problem refers to specifying a classification model that perfectly separates the subsets of the XOR partition P_{XOR} . Due to Radon's theorem Radon (1921) for any $d + 2$ points in \mathbb{R}^d there is a partition into two subsets with intersecting convex hulls. As a consequence, since for a linear classifier L with threshold ϑ the related pre-images $A := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^d : L(x) \geq \vartheta\}$ and $B := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^d : L(x) < \vartheta\}$ form a partition of convex sets, 4 points in \mathbb{R}^2 cannot be shattered by a linear classifier.

In this paper we study the problem under which conditions the set $S = \{(0, 0), (0, 1), (1, 0), (1, 1)\} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ can be shattered by a spiking neural network SNN_W with a single hidden layer and weight matrix W . Fig. 1 illustrates the architecture of such SNNs. We use the XOR problem as a vehicle to get insight into the effect of encoding, the choice of the reset mechanism and the difficulty to find a solution by considering the distribution of weights W . That is, we are looking for an as-simple-as-possible spiking neural network that allows to tune its weight matrix to realize any binary partition of interest.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 outlines related work on the XOR problem in the context of SNNs. Section 3 recalls the LIF model and the recently introduced reset-to-mod modification. Section 4 describes the setup of our experiments and discusses its results.

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Figure 1: Architecture of SNN considered in the paper, consisting of a reservoir R of fully connected hidden leaky integrate-and-fire (LIF) neurons of the same type (same threshold and leaky parameter) with weight matrix W and a linear output classifier L . The encoder weights $E = (1, 0, \dots, 0)$ are fixed, W is generated randomly and the decoder weights D are learned.

2 Related Work

Representing a simple non-linear problem that requires hidden units to transform the input into the desired output, the XOR problem is often considered a benchmark problem for testing neural network capabilities in solving more complex problems. This problem played a remarkable role in the early phase of AI. In their book Minsky and Papert (1969), the neural network pioneers Marvin Minsky and Seymour Papert demonstrated that it is impossible for single-layer perceptrons (also referred to a first generation neural networks) to resolve the XOR problem. Unfortunately, incorrect citations in connection with these findings contributed to a significant decline in interest of neural network research in the 1970s, the so-called *AI winter*. It took another ten years before research in the field of neural networks began to take off in the 1980s Sejnowski (2018). In the meanwhile we encounter the so-called third generation of artificial neural networks in terms of spiking neural networks (SNNs) which are closer to the biological reference model by giving time a crucial role in information encoding and dynamics of the network Maass (1997); Gerstner et al. (2014).

The neurons in a spiking neural network (SNN) generate action potentials, or spikes, when the internal neuron state variable, called *membrane potential*, crosses a threshold. In contrast to conventional neural networks of the first and second generation, this way SNNs interconnect neurons that asynchronously process and transmit spatial-temporal information based on the occurrence of spikes that come from spatially distributed sensory input neurons Dayan and Abbott (2001); Gerstner et al. (2014).

Inspired from biology different information encoding principles with different characteristics have been proposed. Two main coding approaches can be distinguished for SNN-based systems: rate coding and temporal coding. For an overview, see, e.g. Gerstner et al. (2014); Auge et al. (2021). Rate coding aims to represent the intensity of a variable, e.g. voltage, by means of a spike frequency rate. This principle has been known in neurophysiology for many decades Adrian and Zotterman (1926), so it has been experimentally discovered in most sensory systems such as the visual cortex and the motor cortex. However, rate coding comes also with drawbacks such as limitations due to slow information transfer and a long processing time. In contrast, temporal coding techniques use the precise timing of and between spikes to encode information. This includes the absolute timing with some reference, the relative timing of spikes triggered by different neurons, or simply the order in which neurons generate certain spikes.

The various information encoding variants are also taken up to tackle the XOR problem by spiking neural networks Bohte et al. (2002); Wade et al. (2007); Reljan-Delaney and Wall (2017); Enriquez-Gaytan et al. (2018); Matsumoto et al. (2018); Cyr et al. (2020). So, Bohte et al Bohte et al. (2002) demonstrate a proof of concept of their SpikeProp algorithm by utilizing temporal encoding. While 0 is encoded with a *late* firing time and 1 is represented by *early* firing time. The related SNN topology consists of three input neurons (2 coding neurons and 1 reference neuron), 5 hidden neurons and a single output neuron. Due to convergence reasons this model does not allow a mix of both positive and negative weight. Therefore one of the hidden neurons is designed as an inhibitory neuron generating only negative sign spikes. In contrast, other authors such as Wade et al. (2007); Reljan-Delaney and Wall (2017); Enriquez-Gaytan et al. (2018); Cyr et al. (2020) utilize rate encoding by representing 0 by spike trains of some frequency, e.g. 50Hz, and 1 by another frequency, e.g., 100Hz. By mimicking logic gates, in Wade et al. (2007) the SNN topology for the XOR problem consists of two inputs, 2 hidden layers with 4 neurons each, and 2 output neurons, where the the first hidden layer is partially connected, based on neurons that are designed to respond on selected frequency ranges, resulting in two active neurons for any 0-1 combination. In the same spirit, also Reljan-Delaney and Wall (2017) mimics the functionality of logic gates but by utilizing additionally receptive fields between the LIF neurons to realize selective responses input frequencies. The resulting feed-forward SNN also consists of 2 input neurons and 4 LIF neurons in a hidden layer together with additional 2×8 receptive fields (RF) to filter the states (0, 0), (0, 1), (1, 0) and (1, 1), and

two output neurons for 0 and 1, where the final decision is based on the winner-takes-all principle. Cyr et al. (2020) proposes four main layers of LIF neurons based on spike timing-dependent plasticity (STDP) as learning rule. While leaky integrate-and-fire (LIF) is the simplest neuron model for SNNs, also more advanced neuron models such as the Izhikevich neuron are used. Again using rate encoding, Enriquez-Gaytan et al. (2018) studies the XOR problem by means of a feed-forward $2 - 2 - 1$ SNN architecture based on Izhikevich neurons. Its related 16 weights are found by genetic and evolutionary algorithms.

3 LIF Model and Preliminaries

The leaky-integrate-and-fire neuron model (LIF) with leaky parameter $\alpha > 0$ and threshold $\vartheta > 0$ uses integration which determines a recursive procedure to turn a signal f into a spike train $\eta(t) = \sum_k s_k \delta(t - t_k)$, where $s_k \in \mathbb{R}$ denotes the amplitude of the spike at time t_k . The time points t_k are recursively given by

$$t_{k+1} := \inf \left\{ T \geq t_k + t_r : \mathcal{T} \left[\int_{t_k}^T e^{-\alpha(t_{k+1}-t)} (f(t) + r_k \delta(t - t_k)) dt \right] \geq \vartheta \right\}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{T}[x] = x$ is either the identity (only positive threshold), or the modulus, $\mathcal{T}[x] = |x|$ (positive and threshold), $t_r \geq 0$ is the refractory time and $T = t_{k+1}$ is the first time point after t_k that causes the integral in (1) to violate the sub-threshold condition $|\int_{t_k}^T e^{-\alpha(t_{k+1}-t)} f(t) dt| < \vartheta$. The term $r_k \delta(t - t_k)$ refers to the reset of the membrane potential in the moment a spike has been triggered. In the standard definition of LIF for discrete spike trains, see Gerstner et al. (2014), the reset is defined as the membrane potential that results from subtracting the threshold if the membrane’s potential reaches the positive threshold level $+\vartheta$, or adding ϑ to the membrane’s potential if a spike is triggered at the negative threshold level $-\vartheta$. In the case of bounded f the integral $g(t) := \int_{t_k}^t e^{-\alpha(t_{k+1}-t)} f(t) dt$ is changing continuously in t so that the threshold level in (1) is exactly hit. Consequently the resulting reset amounts to zero, i.e., $r_k = 0$ and the resulting amplitude s_k of the triggered spike is defined accordingly, i.e., $s_k = +\vartheta$, when the positive threshold value is reached, and $s_k = -\vartheta$ when the negative threshold value is reached. For a mathematical analysis and a discussion of how to define the reset r_k in the presence of Dirac impulses see Moser and Lunglmayr (2024).

Injecting weighted Dirac pulses the neuron’s potential will show discontinuous jumps, and different reset variants are reasonable from an algorithmic point of view. Beyond the prevalent variants of *reset-to-zero* and *reset-by-subtraction*, see e.g. Eshraghian et al. (2021), recently we introduced *reset-to-mod* as a third option, see Moser and Lunglmayr (2024). *reset-to-zero* means that the neuron’s potential is reinitialized to zero after firing, while *reset-by-subtraction* subtracts the ϑ -potential u_ϑ from the membrane’s potential that triggers the firing event. The third variant, *reset-to-mod*, can be understood as instantaneously cascaded application of *reset-by-subtraction* according to the factor n by which the membrane’s potential u exceeds the threshold, i.e. $u = n\vartheta + r$, $r \in]-\vartheta, \vartheta[$. This means that *reset-to-mod* is the limit case of *reset-by-subtraction* with the refractory time t_r approaching to zero. In this case the residuum r results from a modulo computation and the amplitude of the triggered spike is set to $n\vartheta$.

As listed in Table 1, in total we get 6 LIF neuron model variants depending on the choice of thresholding (only positive, or positive and negative) and the reset variants *reset-to-mod*, *reset-by-subtraction* or *reset-to-zero*.

Table 1: LIF Spiking Neuron Model Variants

Model	Thresholding	Reset
Symmetric Reset-to-Mod (SRM)	positive and negative	reset-to-mod
Symmetric Reset-by-Sub (SRS)	positive and negative	reset-by-subtraction
Symmetric Reset-to-Zero (SRZ)	positive and negative	reset-to-zero
Positive Reset-to-Mod (PRM)	only positive	reset-to-mod
Positive Reset-by-Sub (PRS)	only positive	reset-by-subtraction
Positive Reset-to-Zero (PRZ)	only positive	reset-to-zero

4 Resolving Binary Logical Gates by SNNs

In contrast to the related work outlined in Section 2, our model consists only of a single input neuron and a single output neuron as illustrated in Fig. 1. The hidden layer is realized by a reservoir of N LIF neurons with randomly generated weights Rahimi and Recht (2008). The decision is realized by a classical perceptron by summing up the weighted output spike trains ψ_k , $k = 1, \dots, N$ at neuron L in Fig. 1. Note that the existence whether there is a solution

Figure 2: Enumeration of all binary logical gates where XOR is represented by case 6.

Figure 3: Variants A , A' , B and C for temporal encoding of logical gates by means of mixed positive and negative graded spikes.

or not can be checked by a linear program. If v_i^A denotes the vector of resulting sums for each output channel for the i -th input from the A class, and accordingly, v_j^B for j -th input from class B , then there the classes A and B can be separated linearly if and only if there is a vector D of decoder weights and a threshold ϑ such that for all i, j we have $\langle v_i^A, D \rangle \geq \vartheta$ and $\langle v_j^B, D \rangle < \vartheta$, where $\langle x, y \rangle = \sum_i x_i y_i$ denotes the standard inner product. This solvability problem can equivalently be decided by a homogenous problem with threshold 0 by checking the existence of \tilde{D} such that $\langle \tilde{v}_i^A, \tilde{D} \rangle \geq 0$ and $\langle \tilde{v}_j^B, \tilde{D} \rangle < 0$ for i and j , where \tilde{v}_i^A and \tilde{v}_j^B result from v_i^A , resp. v_j^B , by adding the additional coordinate -1 . In turn, this problem can be equivalently decided by checking whether the set constituted of all \tilde{v}_i^A and $-\tilde{v}_j^B$ can be linearly separated from the origin 0, i.e., whether the convex hull of the points \tilde{v}_i^A and $-\tilde{v}_j^B$ contains 0 or not. This can be done by a linear program to solve for $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ satisfying $Px = 0$, $\sum_k x_k = 1$ and $x_k \geq 0$, where P is the matrix containing the points as column vectors, see, e.g., Matouek and Gärtner (2006).

Our main objective is to investigate the effect of various hyper parameters on the distribution of solutions in the space of weights, that is how difficult it is to find a solution. Besides the XOR problem, we also consider all the other constellations of binary logical gates as illustrated in Fig. 2. For this we consider temporal encoding in different constellations, also allowing mixed positive, negative spikes and spikes with different amplitudes (grades), see Fig. 3. The weights for the fully connected reservoir of LIF neurons are generated randomly based on uniform sampling the interval $[-1, 1]$ with discretization of 0.1. The probability evaluations are based on 100 runs in each considered constellation. Note that the variants A , A' and B of Fig. 3 represent 4 points in 2-dimensional space, whereas this is not the case for C . Therefore, only A or B are representation to which Radon's theorem of non-separability applies. Variant C circumvents the problem by increasing the dimensionality of the space from 2 to 4. Dimensionality enlargement by additional spikes might ease the problem as demonstrated in Table 5, but at the cost of sparseness. For $\beta = 1$ for all LIF variants SRM, SRS, SRZ, PRM, PRS, PRZ one can find solutions, where the probability to find a solution is greater the 10% for SRM and SRS. For $\beta = 0.5$ only for SRM and SRS there are solutions.

While encoding A does not work, the results for encoding variant B and leaky parameters $\beta = 1$, resp. $\beta = 0.5$, are shown in Table 2. Interestingly, our recently introduced *reset-to-mod* variant in terms of SRM (symmetric reset-to-mod) and PRM (positive reset-to-mod) gives the highest probability to find a solution, particularly for PRM with $\beta = 0.5$. Table 3 and Table 4 show the related mean and standard deviation of the l_1 -norm of the output spike train. For PRM with $\beta = 0.5$ we obtain the sparsest solutions for all gates.

Table 2: Solvability probability for encoding B, $E = (1, 0)$, $\beta = 1$ (left), $\beta = 0.5$ (right)

Gate	SRM	SRS	SRZ	PRM	PRS	PRZ	Gate	SRM	SRS	SRZ	PRM	PRS	PRZ
0	30.0	27.5	0.0	49.5	49.5	0.0	0	63.5	22.5	0.0	93.0	25.0	0.0
1	2.5	2.5	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	1	20.0	0.0	0.0	11.5	0.0	0.0
2	3.0	2.5	0.0	1.0	1.5	0.0	2	14.5	0.0	0.0	11.5	0.0	0.0
3	29.5	28.5	0.0	50.0	49.5	0.0	3	70.0	22.5	0.0	95.5	25.0	0.0
4	1.5	3.0	0.0	1.0	5.0	0.0	4	10.5	2.0	0.0	2.5	1.0	0.0
5	4.0	4.5	0.0	0.5	1.5	0.0	5	5.0	2.0	0.0	2.5	1.0	0.0
6	2.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.5	0.0	6	7.5	0.0	0.0	3.0	0.0	0.0

Table 3: Mean of l_1 -norm of output spike train of Table 2, $\beta = 1$ (left), $\beta = 0.5$ (right); "-" means not computable due to no spikes available.

Gate	SRM	SRS	SRZ	PRM	PRS	PRZ	Gate	SRM	SRS	SRZ	PRM	PRS	PRZ
0	12.7	12.8	-	4.4	6.6	-	0	5.9	5.2	-	3.2	4.9	-
1	32.2	37.0	-	5.0	18.0	-	1	24.0	-	-	3.2	-	-
2	41.0	15.6	-	5.0	15.0	-	2	11.4	-	-	3.6	-	-
3	5.6	10.2	-	3.4	4.5	-	3	3.1	3.5	-	2.2	3.4	-
4	31.7	50.3	-	6.0	16.2	-	4	42.0	6.5	-	6.0	7.0	-
5	17.0	27.3	-	6.0	16.0	-	5	7.3	6.5	-	8.8	7.0	-
6	18.8	36.5	-	6.0	8.0	-	6	3.8	-	-	3.8	-	-

5 Conclusion

In this paper we study the problem to realize the decision problems of binary logical gates by means of spiking neural networks based on temporal encoding. It turns out that the choice of hyper parameters in terms of leaky parameter and the design of the reset mechanism in combination with the temporal encoding is crucial. In contrast to the standard setting of *reset-by-subtraction* we consider also *reset-to-mod* which can be understood as an instantaneous charge-discharge event with zero net voltage. It is shown that a temporal encoding of 0 and 1 based on graded spikes in combination with *reset-to-mod* and a reservoir of 2 fully interconnected LIF neurons provides the sparsest solution and that the weights can be found by uniform random initialization with a success rate of at least 3%, in our experiments 3 out of 100 runs. In future research we will also consider a LIF neuron as output layer which requires a generalization of the outlined solvability criterion based on the convex hull argument.

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References

- Johann Radon. Mengen konvexer Körper, die einen gemeinsamen Punkt enthalten. *Mathematische Annalen*, 83: 113–115, 1921. URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:121627696>.
- M. Minsky and S. Papert. *Perceptrons*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, 1969.
- Terrence J. Sejnowski. *The Deep Learning Revolution*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, 2018. ISBN 978-0-262-03803-4.
- Wolfgang Maass. Fast sigmoidal networks via spiking neurons. *Neural Computation*, 9(2):279–304, 02 1997. ISSN 0899-7667. doi:10.1162/neco.1997.9.2.279. URL <https://doi.org/10.1162/neco.1997.9.2.279>.
- Wulfram Gerstner, Werner M. Kistler, Richard Naud, and Liam Paninski. *Neuronal Dynamics: From Single Neurons to Networks and Models of Cognition*. Cambridge University Press, USA, 2014. ISBN 1107635195.
- Peter Dayan and L. F. Abbott. *Theoretical Neuroscience: Computational and Mathematical Modeling of Neural Systems*. The MIT Press, 2001.

Table 4: Standard deviation of l_1 -norm w.r.t Table 3

Gate	SRM	SRS	SRZ	PRM	PRS	PRZ	Gate	SRM	SRS	SRZ	PRM	PRS	PRZ
0	24.4	21.3	-	4.3	5.5	-	0	16.6	1.8	-	2.1	1.6	-
1	47.9	39.6	-	1.0	1.0	-	1	57.7	-	-	0.4	-	-
2	47.4	4.1	-	1.0	4.3	-	2	33.9	-	-	1.7	-	-
3	9.2	25.0	-	3.5	3.7	-	3	1.5	0.9	-	1.3	0.8	-
4	36.3	45.6	-	0.0	3.4	-	4	75.1	0.9	-	2.8	1.0	-
5	25.1	31.8	-	0.0	7.0	-	5	3.2	0.9	-	3.7	1.0	-
6	22.7	28.5	-	1.0	0.0	-	6	1.0	-	-	1.5	-	-

Table 5: Solvability probability for encoding C, $E = (1, 0)$, $\beta = 1$ (left), $\beta = 0.5$ (right)

Gate	SRM	SRS	SRZ	PRM	PRS	PRZ	Gate	SRM	SRS	SRZ	PRM	PRS	PRZ
0	61.0	72.0	66.0	41.0	41.0	40.0	0	87.0	90.0	88.0	39.0	39.0	39.0
1	19.0	30.0	27.0	3.0	3.0	6.0	1	15.0	15.0	14.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
2	24.0	29.0	22.0	7.0	7.0	7.0	2	6.0	6.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
3	57.0	66.0	70.0	59.0	59.0	40.0	3	95.0	98.0	95.0	44.0	44.0	44.0
4	34.0	41.0	27.0	62.0	61.0	38.0	4	39.0	39.0	37.0	44.0	44.0	44.0
5	14.0	17.0	8.0	5.0	5.0	3.0	5	2.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
6	13.0	17.0	8.0	6.0	6.0	3.0	6	11.0	11.0	8.0	5.0	5.0	5.0

Daniel Auge, Julian Hille, Etienne Mueller, and Alois Knoll. A survey of encoding techniques for signal processing in spiking neural networks. *53(6):4693–4710*, 2021. doi:10.1007/s11063-021-10562-2.

E. D. Adrian and Y. Zotterman. The impulses produced by sensory nerve endings: Part 3. impulses set up by touch and pressure. *J Physiol.*, 61(4):465–483, 1926. doi:10.1113/jphysiol.1926.sp002308.

Sander M. Bohte, Joost N. Kok, and Han La Poutré. Error-backpropagation in temporally encoded networks of spiking neurons. *Neurocomputing*, 48(1):17–37, 2002.

John Wade, Liam McDaid, JA Santos, and Heather Sayers. A biologically inspired training algorithm for spiking neural networks. In *Irish Signals and Systems Conference (ISSC)*, pages 7–12, Derry, Sept 2007. Institution of Engineering and Technology.

Mirela Reljan-Delaney and Julie A. Wall. Solving the linearly inseparable XOR problem with spiking neural networks. *2017 Computing Conference*, pages 701–705, 2017.

J. Enriquez-Gaytan, F. Gomez-Castaneda, J.A. Moreno-Cadenas, and L.M. Flores-Nava. Experimental spiking neural network: Solving the XOR paradigm with metaheuristics. In *2018 15th International Conference on Electrical Engineering, Computing Science and Automatic Control (CCE)*, pages 1–5, 2018. doi:10.1109/ICEEE.2018.8533911.

Kazuki Matsumoto, Hiroyuki Torikai, and Hiroo Sekiya. XOR learning by spiking neural network with infrared communications. In *2018 Asia-Pacific Signal and Information Processing Association Annual Summit and Conference (APSIPA ASC)*, pages 1289–1292, 2018. doi:10.23919/APSIPA.2018.8659484.

André Cyr, Frédéric Thériault, and Sylvain Chartier. Revisiting the XOR problem: a neurorobotic implementation. *Neural Comput. Appl.*, 32(14):9965–9973, 2020.

Bernhard A. Moser and Michael Lunglmayr. Spiking neural networks in the Alexiewicz topology: A new perspective on analysis and error bounds. *Neurocomputing*, 601:128190, 2024. ISSN 0925-2312. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2024.128190.

Jason K. Eshraghian, Max Ward, Emre Neftci, Xinxin Wang, Gregor Lenz, Girish Dwivedi, Mohammed Bennamoun, Doo Seok Jeong, and Wei D. Lu. Training spiking neural networks using lessons from deep learning. *arXiv*, 2021. doi:10.48550/ARXIV.2109.12894. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2109.12894>.

Ali Rahimi and Benjamin Recht. Weighted sums of random kitchen sinks: Replacing minimization with randomization in learning. In D. Koller, D. Schuurmans, Y. Bengio, and L. Bottou, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 21. Curran Associates, Inc., 2008. URL https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2008/file/0ef32849d230d7f53049ddc4a4b0c60-Paper.pdf.

Jirí Matouek and Bernd Gärtner. *Understanding and Using Linear Programming (Universitext)*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2006. ISBN 3540306978.

Table 6: Mean of l_1 -norm of output spike train of Table 5, $\beta = 1$ (left), $\beta = 0.5$ (right)

Gate	SRM	SRS	SRZ	PRM	PRS	PRZ	Gate	SRM	SRS	SRZ	PRM	PRS	PRZ
0	8.2	11.6	6.7	7.5	8.3	4.5	0	3.7	3.6	4.0	5.4	5.4	4.0
1	6.2	14.7	5.1	12.3	13.3	5.8	1	7.7	7.7	5.7	6.8	6.8	6.0
2	13.8	6.5	5.0	9.4	9.9	5.7	2	8.0	8.0	5.0	-	-	-
3	4.3	4.1	5.2	3.5	3.5	3.2	3	3.5	3.5	3.2	3.8	3.8	3.1
4	7.5	14.1	12.1	5.7	5.9	4.4	4	6.2	6.2	4.5	5.5	5.5	4.2
5	21.9	25.4	98.6	9.8	10.4	190.0	5	12.0	12.0	-	-	-	-
6	4.5	4.1	26.4	4.7	4.7	3.3	6	5.1	5.1	4.1	4.4	4.4	4.0

Table 7: Standard deviation of l_1 -norm w.r.t Table 6

Gate	SRM	SRS	SRZ	PRM	PRS	PRZ	Gate	SRM	SRS	SRZ	PRM	PRS	PRZ
0	13.4	24.8	21.7	4.2	5.2	1.1	0	2.5	2.5	10.6	1.6	1.6	0.0
1	3.1	33.0	1.6	3.3	3.1	1.1	1	3.0	3.0	1.3	1.6	1.6	0.0
2	33.6	3.6	1.6	3.8	4.1	1.0	2	3.5	3.5	1.5	-	-	-
3	2.4	2.3	11.5	1.7	1.7	0.5	3	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.8	0.8	0.3
4	4.0	28.3	33.2	3.8	3.6	1.1	4	2.3	2.3	1.0	1.6	1.6	0.6
5	42.3	41.1	91.4	3.2	3.1	0.0	5	2.0	2.0	-	-	-	-
6	1.5	1.6	58.8	1.5	1.5	0.5	6	1.4	1.4	0.3	0.8	0.8	0.0